

Effects of Dietary Supplementation of Neem Leaf Powder (Azadirachta Indica) on Growth Performance, Carcass Characteristics and Serum Biochemical Parameters of Broilers

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the effects of dietary supplementation with neem leaf powder (NLP) on the growth performance, carcass characteristics, and serum biochemical parameters of broilers. A total of 225 one-day-old Ross 308 broilers were used in a 35-day experiment using a completely randomized design. The birds were divided into 5 dietary base treatments with 3 replicates of 15 birds per pen. The treatments consisted of supplementation of 0, 2, 2.5, 3, and 3.5 g/kg of NLP to a basal diet. The experiment included an evaluation of the following characteristics: performance, internal organs, and serum biochemical parameters. The results showed that the addition of different levels of NLP to the diet had no significant effect on the growth performance of broilers at different ages. Broilers fed with 2-3.5 g/kg NLP had a smaller breast size compared to the control group, while thigh weight increased linearly. The gizzard's weight showed a linear increase. Other organ weights did not differ significantly. The addition of 3.5 g/kg NLP to the broiler diet increased total protein and albumin levels. ALT, AST, and MDA levels decreased significantly with increasing NLP levels, while SOD and CAT levels increased. Broilers fed 2.5–3.5 g/kg NLP had higher HDL and lower LDL levels compared to the control group. No significant effect was observed on TG, total cholesterol, or VLDL levels. In summary, NLP supplementation in the broiler diet led to smaller breast sizes, increased thigh weight, an improved lipid profile, and enhanced liver health.

Keywords: broiler, growth performance, neem leaf, lipid, and liver.

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Introduction

It was expected, after the widespread use of artificial chemical drugs and their variety, that disease rates would decrease and the ability to control them would be enhanced. However, on the contrary, new diseases have emerged, possibly due to many artificial drugs that attack immunity and the onset of side effects. On the other hand, there are many available plants with great therapeutic uses due to the presence of diverse active materials at reasonable rates without any dangerous side effects on human health (Abbas and Nihad, 2019). Hence, medical plants have started to be a big concern in agricultural products due to the natural chemical materials of big benefit in their physiological effects and therapy activity for human beings and animals. Scientific studies proved that derived products from these plants have the ability to

heal from many diseases and remove syndromes. One of these plants is Neem. Neem leaves contain volatile oils more than roots and these oils contain minerals, iron, calcium, phosphorus, and vitamins C and A (Saleem et al., 2018; Al-Jebory et al., 2023), scientific awareness currently increased for the therapy and medical importance of Neem plus to food importance, most recent experiments showed that is considered one of the oxidation's antibiotics against infection of cancer for cells, fortify the immunity for them because of the C vitamin content that is four times than found in lemon, it is found that every (100) g of Neem contains (165) mg of C vitamin (Saleem et al., 2018) and high rates of phenols especially gallic acid that stop the division of cancer cells so it helps in healing of this disease and reduce its spreading (Shewale and Rathod, 2018). Experiments done by some researchers showed that the extracted oil from Neem is considered an antibiotic for oxidation and an impediment for free radicals (Heyman et al., 2017). This oil contains vitamins A, B, B2, B3, B4, and C, iron salts, calcium, and iodine and is active in the plant (Valarmathy et al., 2010). Extracts of Neem's leaf showed high effectiveness as potent antibiotics against negative and positive bacteria for Gram stain and some fungi (Ezzat et al., 2018). Due to the aforementioned, this study aimed to determine the nutritional value of Neem leaves added to the feed on the productivity and physiology performance of broiler chicks.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Birds, Diet, and Management

This study was implemented in the poultry field belonging to the Department of Animal Production, College of Agriculture, Al-Qasim Green University, for the period from 1/11/2023 to 5/12/2023, using 225 one-day-old Ross 308 broilers of average weight (41 g/chick). Broilers were bought from Alanwar Incubator (Province of Babel). The chicks were weighed and bred in land cages, and then they were randomly distributed into five different treatment groups; each treatment contains three replicates, and each one includes 15 chicks. Feed was served to birds freely; two types of feed were served: (1-21)-day-old chick and (22-35)-day-old chick (table 1). The requirements were calculated according to the Ross 308 Broiler Nutrition Specifications (2022). Throughout the entire experimental period, the birds were provided with free access to fresh drinking water and feed. Adding NLP to the diet (on top) since the first day after hatching, as follows: The treatments consisted of supplementing the basal diet with 0, 2, 2.5, 3, and 3.5 g/kg of NLP. The basal diet of corn-soybean meal was formulated in order to meet or surpass the growth performance.

Data Collection and Record-Keeping

Broilers in different groups were weighed weekly to measure their body weight (BW), body weight gain (BWG), and feed intake (FI). Lambert et al. (1936) proposed the method used to calculate the feed conversion ratio (FCR). At the conclusion of the experiment, researchers slaughtered one randomly selected chick from each replication group. After thorough bleeding, the weight of the beheaded bird, internal organs (heart, gizzard, Fabricius bursa, liver), and the ratio of main and secondary parts of the beheaded bird (carcass weight) were measured. By calculating the weight of each parameter or organ relative to the body weight, the relative weights of dressing parameters (breast, thigh, carcass, and back and neck) and internal organs (liver, heart, fabric, and gizzard) were determined.

Serum Biochemical Analysis

Samples of blood were obtained by collecting them from the jugular vein through slaughtering. We then centrifuged the collected samples at a speed of 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. Following centrifugation, the resulting serum was stored at a temperature of -20°C until it was analyzed. The concentrations of total serum cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), and high-density lipoproteins (HDL) were determined using the methods previously described by Allain et al. (1974), Bucolo and David (1973), and Alen et al. (1979).

In addition, the serum samples were utilized for the detection of various parameters, including serum total protein (Yatzidis, 1977), albumin (Doumas et al., 1972), globulin (whose concentration in serum was calculated by subtracting albumin from total proteins), ALT (alanine aminotransferase), and AST (aspartate aminotransferase) following the method by Reitman and Frankel (1957). Furthermore, the levels of superoxide dismutase (SOD) were determined based on the method described by Nishikimi et al. (1972), while catalase (CAT) was analyzed according to the method established by Goth (1991). We assessed lipid peroxidation (MDA) using the methodology outlined by Buege and Aust (1978).

Statistical Analysis

In this study, a completely randomized design was employed to analyze the data related to BW, BWG, FI, FCR, carcass characteristics, internal organ weights, and serum biochemical parameters of broilers. We utilized the general linear models of SAS (2009) to analyze the variance. To determine any significant differences in mean values, Duncan's multiple range test was applied. We set the level of significance at $P < 0.05$.

Table 1. Ingredients and Analyzed Nutrient Compositions of the Experimental Diets

Ingredient% ¹	Starter	Grower	Finisher
Corn	38.50	42.29	46.80
Soya meal	44.36	40.11	34.55
Wheat	10	10	10
Concentrate	2.5	2.5	2.5
Di Calcium phosphate	0.04	0.0	0.0
Calcium carbonate	1.26	1.07	1.25
Sunflower oil	2.29	3.15	4.08
Sodium chloride	0.17	0.17	0.17
Supplement vitamin & mineral	0.5	0.5	0.5
DL-Methionine (99%)	0.21	1.2	0.12
L-Lysine (99%)	0.09	0.1	0.00
Threonine	0.08	0.05	0.03
Sum	100	100	100
Composition			
ME(kcal/Kg)	3000	3100	3200
C. protein	23	21.5	19.5
Ca	0.96	0.78	0.93
P	0.58	0.56	0.54
Na	0.16	0.16	0.16
Dig. Lysine	1.44	1.29	1.15
Dig. Methionine	0.77	0.70	0.64
Dig. Threonine	0.97	0.88	0.78
Dig. Met + Cys	1.08	0.99	0.90
DCAB	236.23	220.74	200.20
C.F%	5.05	4.84	4.55
Fat%	3.10	3.08	3.04
Linoleic acid%	1.02	1.09	1.17

Note: Provime concentrate produced by Provime (Dutch: Jordanian origin) Each kg contains: 17% crude protein, 1.5% crude fat, 1% fiber, 14% calcium, 6.7% available phosphorus, 4.8% sodium, 5.8% chloride, 13.7% total phosphorus, 9.3% non-lysine, 7.8% methionine + cysteine, 0.4% tryptophan, 2100 kcal/kg energy representative, 480000 IU vitamin A, 220000 IU vitamin D3, 3000 mg vitamin E, 138 mg vitamin K3, 138 mg vitamin B1, 280 mg vitamin B2, 600 mg vitamin B5, 48 mg vitamin B6, 1000 mg vitamin B9, 1800 mg niacin, 6900 mg biotin, 2400 mg iron, 3500 mg zinc, 3200 mg manganese, 480 mg copper, 10

mg selenium, 48 mg iodine, and 250 mg antioxidant. (2) According to each of the energy represented, crude protein, crude fiber, fat, lysine, and methionine + cysteine, calcium, and biophosphorus .

Results

Growth Performance

The effects of dietary treatments on the BW, BWG, FI, and FCR of broilers are shown in Table 2. The results showed that the addition of different levels of NLP to the diet had no significant effect on BW, BWG, FI, and FCR at different ages ($P > 0.05$).

Table 2. Effect of Different Levels of Neem Leaf Powder on Growth Performance of Broiler (g/bird)

Parameters	Treatments (g/kg)					P-value			
	0	2	2.5	3	3.5	SEM	TRT	linear	Quadratic
BW (g/bird)									
7 d	146.46	153.98	152.58	146.88	157.15	4.26	0.37	0.99	0.15
14 d	357.56	368.02	338.87	365.02	355.58	8.38	0.19	0.86	0.37
21 d	731.22	750.51	701.20	755.09	726.27	17.02	0.24	0.77	0.33
28 d	1288.02	1313.49	1257.78	1365.48	1204.13	60.68	0.45	0.52	0.51
35 d	1960.00	1948.81	1960.00	1970.09	1839.68	60.38	0.55	0.85	0.88
BWG(g/bird/w)									
0-7 d	107.62	112.76	111.35	108.58	117.31	4.49	0.59	0.94	0.39
8-14 d	211.10	214.04	186.28	218.14	198.42	10.44	0.25	0.88	0.19
15-21 d	373.67	382.49	362.33	390.07	370.69	18.50	0.84	0.73	0.62
22-28 d	556.79	562.98	556.58	610.39	577.79	43.71	0.89	0.44	0.59
29-35 d	669.21	635.32	702.22	604.32	634.56	48.51	0.67	0.57	0.52
1-35 d	1918.38	1907.59	1918.77	1931.78	1799.84	59.88	0.54	0.85	0.84
FI (g/bird/w)									
0-7 d	91.55	97.60	93.34	98.23	93.71	3.82	0.68	0.37	0.88
8-14 d	289.69	280.24	274.20	288.24	268.31	7.90	0.32	0.76	0.17
15-21 d	447.89	475.00	457.67	481.09	442.71	10.90	0.12	0.21	0.86
22-28 d	924.21	915.45	910.93	973.90	881.62	31.37	0.39	0.32	0.27
29-35 d	878.97	938.17	986.03	975.81	911.90	35.26	0.25	0.05	0.34
1-35 d	2632.31	2707.00	2722.18	2817.28	2598.26	61.09	0.17	0.06	0.87
FCR (g feed/g gain)									
0-7 d	0.85	0.86	0.84	0.90	0.80	0.04	0.66	0.50	0.67
8-14 d	1.39	1.31	1.47	1.32	1.35	0.09	0.71	0.91	0.64
15-21 d	1.21	1.24	1.26	1.23	1.19	0.04	0.85	0.68	0.51
22-28 d	1.67	1.64	1.64	1.61	1.52	0.08	0.79	0.66	0.97
29-35 d	1.32	1.50	1.41	1.62	1.45	0.11	0.49	0.15	0.92
1-35 d	1.37	1.41	1.41	1.45	1.44	0.02	0.37	0.08	0.92

Note: SEM, standard error of the means. BW= Body weight, BWG= Body weight gain, FI= feed intake; FCR= Feed conversion ratio

Carcass Characteristics and Internal Organ Weights

The carcass and internal organ weights of the experimental broiler are presented in Table 6. The measurements performed after slaughter (35 days) show that the breast of broilers fed with 2, 2.5, and 3.5g/kg of NLP in the diet was significantly smaller than the breast of the control group ($P < 0.05$). However, the weight of the thigh did not show any significant differences compared to the control group,

but it increased linearly ($p= 0.03$). Except for the linear increase in gizzard weight ($p= 0.02$), the weight of all other internal organs was not significantly different between the experimental groups ($P>0.05$).

Table 3. Effect of Different Levels of Neem Leaf Powder on Carcass and Internal Organ Weights (35 d)

Item (g/kg)	live weight	carcass	Content in body weight (%)				liver	gizzard	Fabricce	heart
			thigh	breast	back and neck					
0	2088.3	74.31	17.06 ^{ab}	29.82 ^a	18.64	2.27	1.55	0.29	0.73	
2	2296.2	72.37	15.97 ^b	26.10 ^{bc}	18.34	2.22	1.54	0.31	0.46	
2.5	2333.3	72.96	18.16 ^{ab}	26.29 ^{bc}	17.72	2.48	1.84	0.30	0.60	
3	2232.0	75.84	21.03 ^a	27.9 ^{ab}	16.78	2.24	2.06	0.20	0.74	
3.5	2300.0	75.08	21.14 ^a	24.62 ^c	16.60	2.09	2.06	0.27	0.54	
SEM	132.42	2.95	1.26	0.98	0.87	0.17	0.14	0.03	0.09	
P-value										
TRT	0.70	0.90	0.05	0.03	0.41	0.62	0.08	0.29	0.28	
Linear	0.44	0.70	0.03	0.24	0.14	0.82	0.02	0.78	0.74	
Quadratic	0.26	0.43	0.14	0.02	0.72	0.61	0.50	0.14	0.06	

Note: ^{a-c} Within a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). SEM, standard error of the means.

Serum Biochemical Parameters

Total Protein, Albumin, and Globulin

Table 4 shows the effects of adding different levels of NLP to the diet on serum concentrations of total protein, albumin, and globulin in broilers at the end of the 5th week of age. Adding 3.5 g/kg NLP to the diet increased the levels of total protein and albumin in the broiler serum ($P < 0.05$). While there were no significant differences observed among all treatments in terms of the level of globulin ($P > 0.05$).

Table 4. Effect of Different Levels of Neem Leaf Powder on Total Protein, Albumin and Globulin in the Serum of 5-week-old Broiler (mean±SE)

Item (g/kg)	Total protein (g/dl)	Albumin (g/dl)	Globulin (g/dl)
0	3.73±0.32 ^b	1.85±0.27 ^b	1.88±0.37
2	3.73±0.33 ^b	1.90±0.29 ^b	1.82±0.26
2.5	4.62±0.15 ^{ab}	2.34±0.15 ^{ab}	2.22±0.05
3	4.79±0.40 ^{ab}	2.18±0.11 ^{ab}	2.61±0.35
3.5	5.30±0.33 ^a	2.82 ±0.03 ^a	2.48±0.30
Level of significance	*	*	NS

Note: ^{a-b} Within a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). SEM, standard error of the means.

Liver Enzymes and Oxidation Criteria

The results of the analysis of liver enzymes and oxidation criteria in broilers are shown in Table 5. The levels of Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and Malondialdehyde (MDA) in broiler serum significantly decreased by treatments of NLP increasing in diet ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, increasing NLP levels in the diet led to elevated levels of superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) ($P < 0.05$).

Table 5. Effect of Different Levels of Neem Leaf Powder on Liver Enzymes and Oxidation Criteria in the Serum of 5-week-old Broiler (mean±SE)

Item (g/kg)	ALT (IU/L)	AST (IU/L)	SOD (U/g)	CAT (U/g)	MDA (nmol/g)
0	15.13±0.59a	23.49±0.57a	349.10±30.75c	13.69±5.89c	22.37±14.0a
2	12.79±0.30b	21.13 ±0.71b	415.97±19.95b	15.25±3.63b	18.00±9.01b
2.5	11.15±0.31c	20.43 ±0.52bc	452.31 ±3.79ab	16.64±6.67ab	16.53±4.56bc
3	10.84±0.17c	20.33±0.50bc	480.77±8.21a	17.05±5.47 ab	16.00±9.02bc
3.5	11.11±0.40c	18.84 ±0.34c	493.80±2.3a	17.46±7.48 a	14.77±2.84c
Level of significance	*	*	*	*	*

Note: ^{a-c} Within a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). SEM, standard error of the means; ALT= Alanine aminotransferase, AST= Aspartate aminotransferase, SOD= Superoxide dismutase, CAT= Catalase, MDA= Malondialdehyde

Blood Lipid Profile

The effects of different levels of NLP on the lipid profile in the serum of 5-week-old broilers are presented in Table 6. Broilers fed NLP at 2.5, 3, and 3.5 g/kg of diet showed significantly higher HDL and lower LDL levels compared to the control group ($P < 0.05$). HDL and LDL levels at 2 g/kg were statistically similar to those of the control group. The results indicate that NLP had no effect ($P > 0.05$) on TG, serum total cholesterol, or VLDL in the serum of broilers.

Table 6. Effect of Different Levels of Neem Leaf Powder on Lipid Profile in the Serum of 5-week-old Broiler (mean±SE)

Item (g/kg)	Cholesterol (mg/100ml)	Triglyceride (mg/100ml)	HDL (mg/100ml)	LDL (mg/100ml)	VLDL (mg/100ml)
0	2.57±172.74	192.44±6.80	91.38±2.33 ^b	87.25 ±14.05 ^a	38.48 ±1.36
2	204.07±10.14	174.66±13.80	91.52±10.40 ^b	77.63±6.00 ^a	34.92±2.75
2.5	192.78±3.87	175.66±8.50	109.71±5.90 ^a	47.93±5.94 ^b	35.12±1.70
3	194.96±3.46	176.10±5.10	126.79±1.92 ^a	32.95±4.67 ^b	35.21±1.02
3.5	190.53±6.06	173.30± 3.99	127.82±1.65 ^a	28.05±4.30 ^b	34.65±0.80
Level of significance	NS	NS	*	*	NS

Note: ^{a-b} Within a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($P < 0.05$). SEM, standard error of the means.

LDL= Low density lipoprotein, HDL= High density lipoprotein, VLDL= Very low-density lipoprotein

Discussion

Growth Performance

Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), due to its antimicrobial properties and growth promotion characteristics, is a special herb for animal and bird feed (Jawad et al., 2014). It has been stated that the antimicrobial and anti-protozoal characteristics of neem helped to decrease the microbial load of the broiler and improved its performance (Akter et al., 2014). However, the neem characteristics are differently reported in broilers. The results showed that the neem leaf powder supplement had no effect on the body weight of the broiler. In contrast to our results, Mali et al. (2020) reported that the inclusion of neem leaf powder (10 mg/kg) in the diet improved the live body weight, mean weight gain, and FCR of the broiler compared to the control. Manwar et al. (2007) reported that adding 1-2 mg/kg neem leaf powder increased the live body weight of broilers. Ahmed et al. (2014) showed that the body weight of broilers was increased by

adding 1% neem seed cake to their diet. Sarkar et al. (2014) observed that broilers fed with 1% neem leaf extract gained significantly higher body weight. In agreement with our results, in another experiment, no significant difference was observed in feed intake when broilers were fed the neem leaf powder supplement (Mali et al., 2020). Also, Alam et al. (2015) indicated that FCR was not significant in all neem treatments compared to the control group of broilers. In our study, there is a possibility that broiler rearing in stable and stress-free conditions could not show the effects of neem feeding.

Carcass Characteristics and Internal Organ Weights

The carcass characteristics and weight of internal organs of broiler chickens fed dietary levels of neem leaf powder showed no significant effect. In agreement with our study, Mali et al. (2020) reported a non-significant effect on the weight of internal organs of broiler-fed dietary levels of neem leaf powder (5, 10, and 15 mg/kg). Also, Kharde et al. (2014) reported that carcass parameters like dressing yield and giblet yield (heart, gizzard, and liver) were not significantly affected by the supplementation of neem leaf powder. In a study, dietary supplementation with dried neem leaf extract at 0.5% or 2.0% levels had no significant effect on the weights of the pectoral muscle, leg muscles, heart, liver, or abdominal fat tissue of broilers at 35 days of age (Nakamura et al., 2022). In contrast, Akter et al. (2014) showed that the relative weight of the heart, gizzard, liver, and pancreas of birds increased significantly in the 10 gram neem leaf powder-treated group compared to the control group after 30 days post-treatment. Generally, some of the studies reported that Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf powder had no effect on broiler chicken carcass properties (Ubua et al., 2019; Bonsu et al., 2012). It could be due to the lack of a negative effect of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf powder in the trial, as greater quantities of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf powder in the diet had no effect on the birds (Gobezie, 2022).

Serum Biochemical Parameters

Total Protein, Albumin, and Globulin

The results of this study showed the addition of neem leaf powder increased total protein and albumin levels in the serum of broilers. These results showed that these broilers were probably not stressed by feeding the neem leaf extract. Birds fed neem leaf extract may indicate the values of these blood parameters due to better nutrient availability and utilization in the birds. It is possible that the broilers were correctly fed and could obtain essential amino acids and minerals necessary for the normal functioning of the hemopoietic tissues (Nnenna et al., 2013). It is clear from the results that there is an improvement in the concentration of total protein and albumin that was raised in the treatment of Neem's leaf compared with the control treatment, which may be because the content of Neem's leaf of lyxerzene and glycerin acid, which has a similar role as steroid hormones that work on increasing proteins and decrease its analysis that increase growth rates of muscles and bones plus its big role in increasing metabolism (Nok et al., 1993), increases protein concentration in plasma of blood due to the increase of protein plasma of blood as proteins of plasma, especially albumin, works on transferring carbohydrates and fat acids (Varley et al., 1980). increasing rates of Neem, vitamins, some mineral elements, and some hormones like thyroxin will work on decreasing the concentration of low-density lipoproteins in blood plasma (Al-Jebory and others, 2023) showed that Neem's leaves have the effect of decreasing rates of these proteins due to the increase in metabolism, which reflects on increasing the activity of the thyroid and more secretion of the thyroxin hormone.

In agreement with our study, Shihab et al. (2017) reported that broilers fed with neem powder had a higher concentration of albumin and total serum protein. Also, some studies stated that neem leaf powder in diets had a significant effect on blood serum and increased blood sugar while cholesterol decreased (Tollba et al., 2009; Obikaonu et al., 2011). In contrast, Sharma et al. (2015) reported that the serum biochemical profiles of *E. coli*-infected broiler chickens fed neem leaf extracts revealed a significant decrease in TP and albumin concentrations. The several results observed by the researchers on the serum

effect of Neem extracts may, however, depend on the method of application, concentration, and exposure time.

Liver Enzymes and Oxidation Criteria

Some of the tropical tree leaves, like Neem leaves, include bioactive compounds that can affect nutrient utilization in feed (Biswas et al., 2002; Akpan et al., 2008). These bioactive compounds probably modified the hematological and serum biochemical parameters of animals. The ALP enzyme, which is associated with the bile ducts, bone marrow, and placenta, increases in the presence of liver or bone marrow disorders or tumors. When certain organs and tissues, such as the liver and heart, are injured, an enzyme called AST is released into the bloodstream. When the liver, kidney, or lung are damaged by a tumor, high levels of AST are released (Jawad et al., 2014). Based on the findings of Winiarska-Mieczan et al. (2021), the activities of SOD, CAT, and GSH in the muscle tissue of broiler chickens can be enhanced by exogenous antioxidants, thereby providing protection against peroxidation of cellular membranes. In a study by Kumar et al. (2021), it was observed that the supplementation of ascorbic acid and *Moringa oleifera* to broiler chickens raised in tropical conditions resulted in increased activities of CAT, SOD, and GSH, while significantly reducing lipid peroxidation. These effects were attributed to the ability of the aforementioned antioxidants to bind to the cytoplasmic membrane and inhibit oxidases. Our results showed that as the level of neem leaf powder increased in the diet, the levels of ALP and AST decreased, indicating no toxic effect within the liver parenchyma of the broiler. In agreement with our results, Obikaonu et al. (2011) showed that the level of liver enzymes was decreased by increasing the concentration of leaf Neem in the broiler diet.

The significant improvement in treatments of Neem's leaves liver enzymes, oxidation criteria plus the concentration of lipoproteins high density is due to the content of Neem's leaves of some active compounds like basic oils, as (Al-Jebory et al., 2023) and others showed that Neem's leaf have the ability to melt the outside membrane of morbid bacteria and enter the inside of bacterial cell and changes its basic contents, plus it contains active compounds like phenol compounds plus vitamin E that leads to raise the level of antibiotics hence improve the immunity of birds against diseases, both of Nihad and Dakhil, (2022) stated that using medical plants lead to improve the immunity of poultry due to the development of the ratio between assistant and frustrating lymph and enhancing the activity of natural killer cells or activation the lymph cells to produce antibiotics and boosting the bone marrow to produce white cells and increasing producing some cytokines from lymph due to the effect of some active compounds like thiamine and tannic acid.

Neem leaves have high antioxidant activity (Prakash et al., 2007; Heyman et al., 2017) because they are rich in phenolic compounds like ferulic acid and gallic acid (Singh et al., 2005; Shewale and Rathod, 2018). Gallic acid and ferulic acid are phenolic compounds that have been detected in the plasma and thigh meat of chickens (Muñoz-González et al., 2019). Similar to our results, in the Nakamura et al. (2022) study, the effects of dried neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf extract supplement were investigated on the malondialdehyde (MDA) level in the skeletal muscle of broilers. They showed that dietary supplementation with 0.5% to 2% dried neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf extract decreased MDA concentration in the skeletal muscle of broilers. The higher total polyphenol content and free radical scavenging activity of neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf extract might reduce the muscle MDA level in broiler chickens (Nakamura et al., 2022).

Blood Lipid Profile

Neem leaf powder did not affect cholesterol, triglyceride, and VLDL levels, but it increased HDL and decreased LDL. In contrast to our results, Obikaonu et al. (2011) showed that the level of serum cholesterol was decreased by the addition of Neem leaves to the broiler diet. In agreement with our study, Hossain et al. (2022) reported that serum biochemical parameters like TG and serum total serum cholesterol were not affected by neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf powder. Also, these researchers showed

neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf powder increased HDL compared to the control group. This result was similar to Mafouo Sonhafouo et al. (2019) finding that HDL was increased by graded levels of neem oil in the broiler diet. HDL is called good cholesterol and is related to protection from cardiovascular disease because it has high antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities (Hossain et al., 2022). Also, Mohamed et al. (2010) indicated that Neem contains a hepatoprotective factor because of the antioxidant and normalization of impaired membrane function activity.

Conclusion

It was concluded that Neem leaf's powder might be used as a hepatoprotectant in a broiler diet without any toxic effects. Therefore, we can state that the herbal product neem leaf powder had no negative effects on the growth performance of broiler chickens when supplemented within the range of 2 to 3.5 g/kg of diet.

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No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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All authors are either employed by, or associated with, a government agency or university, whose primary function is research and education.

Author Contributions

Ali Almamury: Correspondence, conceptualisation; data curation; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; project administration; resources; software; writing – original draft; writing – review & editing; Visualization.

Majeed Ajafar: conceptualisation; funding acquisition; methodology; supervision, validation.

Nihad Abdul Lateef Ali: conceptualisation & editing; supervision, validation, methodology.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Ethics Statement and Statement of Animal Rights

All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration

and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. All procedures were approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee of the Al-Qasim Green University ,Babylon 51013, Iraq.

Consent to Participate

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Consent to Publish

The authors affirm that human research participants provided informed consent for publication of the images in tables 1-6.

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